

Some New Hydrocupreidine Derivatives. Part I.

BY SUDHAMOY GHOSH AND NIHAR RANJAN CHATTERJEE.

The alkyl ethers of hydrocupreine, like ethyl-, isopropyl-, isoamyl-, and iso-octyl derivatives have been all synthesised (Heidelberger and Jacobs, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 1091; Giemsa and Halberkann, *Ber.*, 1918, **51**, 1325) and found to possess marked bactericidal or local anaesthetic properties. The study of the hydrocupreidine derivatives appears, however, to have been limited only to the ethyl derivative and we thought it desirable to synthesise them for a similar study. As the isoalkyl derivatives of hydrocupreine are known to be more active than the normal compounds we took up the preparation of the *iso*-series of the hydrocupreidines first. The preparation of the normal series is also nearing completion.

The starting material in our preparations was hydroquinidine which was demethylated to hydrocupreidine by boiling with hydrobromic acid (Heidelberger and Jacobs, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 817). The OH-group thus set free was then alkylated. Heidelberger and Jacobs prepared the ethyl hydrocupreidine by the process outlined in D. R. P. 254712 applied in the case of hydrocupreine derivatives and mentioned below as "cold process." We first prepared the isopropyl-, isobutyl-, isoamyl- and secondary octyl hydrocupreidine by the cold process but as it took a long time to complete and the yield was low we modified it by warming with a catalyst as described below. The yield was increased and there was considerable economy of time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

*iso*Propylhydrocupreidine, $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2$.

(a) *By Cold Process.*—The hydrocupreidine (3 g.) was dissolved in a little absolute alcohol and treated with the calculated quantity of 50% potassium hydroxide. The mixture was warmed on the water-bath until clear, cooled in an ice-chest and then treated with isopropyl iodide. The solution was allowed to stand at room

temperature for a month and then chilled to 0° and filtered from potassium iodide. The filtrate was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The aqueous liquid was then made strongly alkaline with caustic soda and shaken with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water and evaporated. The isopropylhydrocupreidine thus obtained was recrystallised from 50 % alcohol (yield, 2.02 g.).

(b) *By Modified Process.*—The hydrocupreidine (6 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol and treated with the calculated quantity of 50 % potassium hydroxide. It was warmed on the water-bath until clear, cooled and treated with isopropyl iodide and freshly prepared copper paste obtained from one gram of copper sulphat. The mixture was boiled on the water-bath under reflux for about 3 hours and the product poured into dilute hydrochloric acid. It was then shaken with ether, the aqueous liquid filtered, made strongly alkaline with caustic soda and the base extracted with ether. The ethereal liquid was washed, shaken with dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated with sodium hydroxide. It was then recrystallised from 50 % alcohol (yield 4.4 g.).

The base crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 181° . It was readily soluble in alcohol, chloroform and ether but insoluble in water. It gave a beautiful blue fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. $[\alpha]_D^{30} = +206.25^{\circ}$ ($c=2$, in absolute alcohol). (Found: N, 7.69. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.90 per cent.).

isoPropylhydrocupreidine Hydrochloride, $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$.—It was prepared by treating the base with dilute hydrochloric acid in aqueous suspension and recrystallised from alcohol. It formed colourless plates, melting at 249° to a brown liquid. It was soluble in water and alcohol. $[\alpha]_D^{30} = +260^{\circ}$ ($c=1$, in $N/10$ -hydrochloric acid. (Found: Cl, 16.21. $C_{22}H_{30}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires Cl, 16.60 per cent.).

isoButylhydrocupreidine, $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2$.—By the cold process 5.2 g. of hydrocupreidine gave 1.5 g. of the base and by the hot process 10.4 g. gave 4.65 g. The base could not be crystallised from ordinary solvents and it was purified by repeated precipitation from the acid solutions. (Found: N, 7.13. $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.60 per cent.).

isoButylhydrocupreidine Hydrochloride, $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2 \cdot 2HCl$.—It was obtained in the usual way and slowly crystallised *in vacuo* in

long colourless needles. It was freely soluble in water and alcohol and partially so in chloroform. It melted at 211° to a dark liquid with previous blackening. $[\alpha]_D^{23} = +212^{\circ}$ ($c=1$, in water). (Found: Cl, 15.81; N, 5.96. $C_{23}H_{32}O_2N_2$, 2HCl requires Cl, 16.08 N, 6.35 per cent.).

isoAmylhydrocupreidine, $C_{24}H_{34}O_2N_2$.—6.2 G. of hydrocupreidine gave 1 g. of the base by the cold process and 9 g. gave 4.7 g. of the base by the hot process. It crystallised from 50 % alcohol in tufts of colourless needles, m.p. 168° . It was soluble in absolute alcohol, ether, chloroform and benzene. It gave a beautiful fluorescence with dilute sulphuric acid. $[\alpha]_D^{30} = +204^{\circ}$ ($c=2$, in absolute alcohol). (Found: N, 7.15. $C_{24}H_{34}N_2O_2$ requires N, 7.33 per cent.).

isoAmylhydrocupreidine Hydrochloride, $C_{24}H_{34}O_2N_2$, 2HCl.—It was prepared in the usual way and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in microscopic needles, m.p. 229° (decomp). $[\alpha]_D^{23} = +215^{\circ}$ ($c=1$, in water). (Found: Cl, 15.45. $C_{24}H_{34}O_2N_2$, 2HCl requires Cl, 15.58 per cent.).

Secondary Octylhydrocupreidine Hydrochloride, $C_{27}H_{40}O_2N_2$, 2HCl.—9 G. of hydrocupreidine gave only 0.5 g. of the base by the cold process and 9 g. gave 1.5 g. of the base by the hot process. It could not be crystallised from the usual solvents. The hydrochloride crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m.p. 227° (decomp.). It was soluble in hot water and alcohol and partially so in chloroform and benzene. It was less soluble in cold water and acetone. $[\alpha]^{32} = +197.0^{\circ}$ ($c=1$, in N/25-hydrochloric acid). (Found: Cl, 13.93; N, 5.13. $C_{27}H_{40}O_2N_2$, 2HCl requires Cl, 14.15; N, 5.59 per cent.).

Summary.

1. The preparation of some new hydrocupreidine derivatives, *isopropyl*-, *isobutyl*-, *isoamyl*- and *sec.-octylhydrocupreidines*, are described, the corresponding isomeric hydrocupreines being all physiologically active.

2. The 'cold process' for the preparation of alkyl hydrocupreines was found to be tedious, uneconomical and unsatisfactory regarding yield, when applied to hydrocupreidines. The method has been improved upon.

3. The pharmacological and other properties are being studied.

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DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
SCHOOL OF TROPICAL MEDICINE AND HYGIENE,
CALCUTTA.

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